

INVESTIGATING THE SUCCESS FACTORS OF THE INNOVATIVE WEB-BASED TRAINING AND CAREER DEVELOPMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract

The necessity is the mother of invention. For that, this study was proposed and developed innovative web-based training and career development system to bridge the gap between industry expectation and academic preparation. The innovative system plays a significant and supportive role as a separate identity in parallel to the USM University e-learning Moodle. This innovative system will provide students with a comfortable learning environment by integrating well-designed industry certified e-training courses. The objective of this study is to provide a model for measuring the success factors of the innovative web-based training and career development system before its full implementation at the entire USM university and other Malaysian universities. Based on DeLone and McLean Information System Success Model (2003), our theoretical argument suggests that in anticipating of the success of a system, the interaction of system quality, information quality and service quality via user satisfaction and the use of the system are critical. We further suggest that this pattern of interaction is especially valuable when interacting with relatively achievement-oriented users who appreciate the training and career development opportunity. Finally, our theoretical framework indicates how the model

facilitates system quality, information quality and service quality by positively mediating the effects of user satisfaction and the use of the system on the likelihood that the system will be successful. Quantitative methods will be applied to achieve the aims of this study. By using SPSS & Smart PLS, the results will be analysed. The hypotheses for this study will be tested with a sample of USM undergraduates' students.

1 INTRODUCTION

Such as many different countries around the world, the institutions of higher learning (IHLs) in Malaysia are now expected to assure that their graduates meet the work requirements. This assumption is applied by providing students with the required skills. At that point, IHLs will produce graduates who are employable and thus generating returns for both individuals and the national economy [1]. The world bank and Talent corporation (TalentCorp) surveyed in Malaysia and—revealed that 80% of companies viewed that the current curriculum needs to address the continuously changing reality of the modern working world [2]. Furthermore, many studies highlighted that there is a mismatch between industry expectation and academic preparation and this existing mismatch needs to be addressed and filled by many efforts [3], [4], [5], [6], [7].

Firstly, the mismatch between industry expectation and academic preparation may have an impact on the graduate employability globally and locally. UNESCO (2007) stated that there are numerous identified issues related to this trend of unemployment such as: deficiency of soft skills; lack of exposing students to the realities of the work; incompatibility of qualifications with industry operators and employers' needs; lack of appropriate career guidance and information; lack of labour market information related to the supply and demand; and economic issues. Therefore, it is clear that the demands and the new requirements for skilled and expert employees change over time [8].

In Malaysia, 10 in 100 youths are unemployed compared to three in 100 workers of all ages. This makes the youth unemployment rate staggering registered 10.8% in 2017 which is three times higher than the national average unemployment rate [9],[10]. While the World Bank reported that Malaysian employers are struggling to source talent, one in four graduates has remained jobless six months after graduation [9],[11]. The high rate of graduate unemployment indicates that the Malaysian tertiary institutions are not producing the workforce that is needed by the market and a clear skills mismatch stay prevalent [9].

Secondly, the mismatch will lead to reducing the number of competitive graduates who are expected to supply themselves with the necessary soft and hard skills to remain competitive and assured employment. A survey conducted by the Confederation of British Industry (CBI) and Pearson (2015,2016) concluded that with the increasing worldwide demand for employees with higher-level skills, it was noticed that the graduate recruiters declare their needs for employees who have the accurate attitudes and aptitudes for work, who own work-relevant or employability skills, and have appropriate work experiences[12],[13].

Recently, there is an evidence that the communication skills considered the No.1 soft skills required to make graduates qualified to be hired [14],[15]. Moreover, Singh et al. [16] indicated that the attributes of the 21st Century (problem-solving and critical thinking, decision-making, communication skills, analytical skills, teamwork, independence, and lifelong learning) have extremely become a cornerstone of graduates' employability. They also evident that there is a clear mismatch between Institutions of higher learning and employers in Malaysia related to the expectations of graduate attributes [16].

Lastly, as the new graduates require extra time to gain new skills to become independent workers, the employer may need to provide additional allocation on and off the job training. Unavoidably, this may delay the process of getting a competent and an effective output unit [17].

For the time being, when the excessive training and retraining are needed, they will add to the production cost, and lead to make the industries less competitive. For this reason, they would be unfavourable to the employers [18].Malaysians' graduates face significant challenges to become work-readiness. These major challenges include the unreasonable expectations of graduates, lack of the industry training and development systems, and the continuous increase in the graduates' numbers [19]. Verma et al. [19] have noted that the Malaysians' stakeholders (government, industry, and educational institutions) arise a concern about the lack of linkages between industry and educational institutions, and they expressed the urgent need to improve the graduates' work-readiness skills by an immediate action to build a strengthened partnership between the two parties (industry and educational institutions). Furthermore, they stated that there is a necessity to involve the industry more in the curriculum development [19].

For this reason, we propose an innovative web-based training and career development system to fulfil the urgent needs to have an automated collaboration platform that will use to link industry with academic institutions.

2 WEB-BASED TRAINING AND CAREER DEVELOPMENT SYSTEM

The innovative web-based training and career development system will play a supportive role as a separate identity in parallel to the basic USM e-learning Moodle for modernising teaching and learning. The primary objective for this system is to link industry with the university through bridging the existing gap between industry expectation and academic preparation by producing employable certified graduates. The system will provide students with a comfortable learning environment by integrating well-designed and certified industry e-training courses. The system incorporates both the social and collaborative features. The system plays a significant role in helping students to develop their employability skills, and personal attributes.

The offered e-training courses are focused on enhancing students' hard skills and soft skills. The offered e-training courses and career path video series which are integrated in the system are essential to ensure that the system will produce employable graduates who are confident to plan and choose their preferred career. The interactivity of these technology environment will give students a clear picture of the real-life work environment and is an important feature for students learning.

3 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND

HYPOTHESIS FORMULATION

To present a model for measuring the innovative web-based training and career development system success, DeLone & McLean (2003) model of information systems success measurement will be used. Previously, in 1992, Delone and McLean presented a model of IS success measurement to examine the information systems success [20]. The same model, in 2003, was revised and developed by Delone & McLean because the role of the information systems is continuously changing over time.

D&M revised model includes six dimensions: (1) information quality, (2) system quality, (3) service quality, (4) use/intention to use, (5) user satisfaction and (6) net benefits [20],[21]. The D&M (2003) model stands as one of the most commonly used models of IS success and has been used for numerous information systems. The E-learning systems are a particular type of IS [22],[21], and learners utilise these systems to learn [23].

Similarly, the innovative web-based training and career development system share the learning feature with an e-learning system. For this reason, the Delone and McLean (2003) model can be used for measuring the success of innovative web-based training and career development system. This study aims to develop a conceptual model for determining the success of the proposed innovative system. For this purpose, various studies were reviewed, and Delone & Mclean information systems success model proposed to be used [20]. The key success factors for evaluating of the innovative web-based training and career development system will be as the main variables of this study as follow: System quality, information quality, and service quality are considered as independent variables, use and user satisfaction

are playing a role of mediator, and the success of the system is considered as the dependent variable. Figure 1 presents the proposed research model.

Figure 1: The proposed research model

4 Research methodology

This study aims to explore the success factors of the innovative web-based training and career development system. The starting point of the proposed study is to set an initial test for the system at one chosen school at USM university. The targeted respondents will be USM students who have used the proposed system throughout the semester. A survey will be conducted in the form of a questionnaire. The structured questionnaire will be developed based on a review of the extant literature as assistance to gain conceptual and measurement information related to variables being examined. The questionnaire will be distributed to the users using the online method. As a result, the written questionnaire will be comprised the following variables: information quality, system quality, service quality, use, user satisfaction and success of the proposed system. Furthermore, demographic information will be included. All constructs that will be investigated in the study by using a seven-point Likert-type scale that is related to the participants' level of agreement with each statement. The scale ranges from "strongly disagree" (1) to "strongly agree" (7).

IBM SPSS & PLS software will be utilised to analyse the proposed measurement model.

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